

Original Article

CONSTRAINTS TO EFFECTIVE HARNESSING OF THE FULL POTENTIAL OF ACCOUNTING EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN UNIVERSITIES IN ENUGU STATE FOR GRADUATES “EMPLOYABILITY”

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the constraints to effective harnessing of the potentials of Accounting Education programme for graduates' employability in universities in Enugu State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was 119 comprised of 22 Accounting Education lecturers and 97 final year students of accounting education programme) in the three universities. The entire population was used because of the size therefore, there was no sampling and sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire titled Constraints to Effective Harnessing of the Potentials of Accounting Education Programme for Graduates' Employability (CEHPAEPG). The instrument contained 20 items in two clusters of 10 items each according to the research questions with response options ranging from strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD). The instrument was face validated by the three experts, two from Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one in Measurement and Evaluation from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both in Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. After editorial corrections, the instrument was said to be valid and used for reliability and data collection. Reliability coefficient values of 0.79 and 0.74 were obtained for the two clusters of the instrument with an overall coefficient value of 0.77 using Cronbach Alpha. Out of 119 copies of questionnaire distributed, 102 copies were properly filled and returned giving 85.71% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and in order to determine the homogeneity of the respondents' mean ratings while t-test was used to test the six null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 100 degree of freedom. Findings of the study revealed that all the listed government and institution-related items are the constrain effective harnessing of the full potential of Accounting Education programme in the universities and that gender did not significantly influence the respondents' mean ratings. Based on the findings, it was concluded that government and institutional related constraints should be addressed by the stakeholders in Accounting Education programme. It was, therefore, recommended among others that government and management of the institutions should implement policies that will address the identified constraints to ensure effective harnessing of the full potential of Accounting Education for the benefits of students, the state and the nation.

Keywords: Accounting Education, Graduate Employability, Constraints to Skill Development, Higher Education Institutions, Enugu State Universities

Introduction

The growth and development of any nation depends, to a great extent, on the quality of the educational programmes provided to the citizenry. Education is a factor for economic and social changes, and a major tool for achieving sustainability. Education is a continuous process of modifying and shaping behaviours of individuals for adequate adjustments in the society. According to Alio, Mbah and Ideh (2023), education is a process of facilitating learning, acquiring knowledge and skills, values, beliefs and habits. It is essential for personal development, societal progress and advancement of knowledge and innovation. Ibekwe (2017) defined education as the process of acculturation through which the individual is helped to sustain the development of his potentials and maximum activation when necessary thereby achieving self-fulfillment. One of the threatening challenges faced by individuals, families and the nation at large in the face of technological influx is the persistent massive graduate turnout from universities without employment.

The rate of unemployment in Nigeria is no doubt appalling and shocking. Agogbua and Mgbatogu (2022) for instance, reported that about 8 million Nigerians are unemployed; not inclusive of 14.4 million that are underemployed, suggesting that 4% of the unemployed in the world are Nigerians. This alarming rate of unemployment could be linked to the inability of some young graduates and active youth to access quality education for knowledge and skills needed for paid or self-employment. Okeke (2017) opined that graduates' inability to demonstrate and exhibit knowledge and skills in problem solving situations in accounting depicts that they were not effectively taught.

In the light of this socio-economic challenge, Nigeria government and higher educational institution have been making concerted efforts to ensure that the students harness the full potential of the curriculum contents of educational programmes for employability skills in order to reduce graduate to

reducing unemployment. Accordingly, higher educational institutions including universities have been endeavouring to imbue the students with requisite instructional packages that are essential for sustainable development. University is the tertiary educational institution that awards degree to students in different disciplines at sub-professional and professional as well as training of high-level manpower. There are public universities (federal and state owned and managed universities) and private universities in Nigeria with the National Universities Commission (NUC) as the regulatory body. These universities are expected to provide training to the students in contemporary issues, curriculum contents as well as entrepreneurship irrespective of economic and environmental challenges in different programmes. Ejiogu (2018) posited that universities play a vital role in providing affordable and accessible education to a diverse range of students, contributing to societal development, research advancements, and economic growth. The instructional delivery at this level of education is expected to equip the learners for gainful employment upon graduation and address the needs of the society at large. Accounting Education is one of the educational programmes offered in Nigerian universities.

Accounting Education is the type of education that provides individual with skills and knowledge in accounting, computing and data processing occupation for gainful employment in private and public enterprise or for self-employment. Nwokike (2015) observed that accounting education provides a training and retraining for students in order to develop capacity in teaching accounting and process documents of business financial performance. Accounting education provides students with information needed for decision making and exposes them to various uses of such information. Accounting as defined by Obayi (2015) is the process of keeping adequate record of financial and non-financial transactions made, properly classifying

them, ensuring its detailed evaluation and insightful analysis, and carefully ensuring that its report to users are timely for possible decision making.

Okafor (2017) stressed that accounting education is a component of business education that is designed with the aim of preparing students for career as professional accountants. It is posed to produce accountants and accounting educators whose integrity will be very transparent and pleasing to better the nation. Akamobi (2020) states that accounting education is relevant to the students for the following reasons- accounting is a tool for developing basic awareness of the contribution which business makes to the Nigerian economy, it helps in improving personal qualities and building attitudes necessary to personal employment, it is the tool and language of business. The field of accounting offers courses that prepare students to constantly meet up with the demands in the labour market. The accounting profession has come under close examination due to changing technology and globalization of the world economy. given to information and communications technology evolution.

Moreover, it is imperative to note that this educational programme is designed to equip students with necessary skills and competencies for successful establishment and operation of business ventures. Such skills include opportunity recognition, creativity, innovation and risk taking as well as the ability to plan and organize businesses in order to achieve desirable goals. Obidile, Amobi, Uzoekwe and Akuezilo (2017) state that most graduates are deficient in terms of the necessary skills and competencies required to make them self-employed. Harnessing accounting education in Nigeria is critical for the nation's economic development and global competitiveness. Harnessing accounting education programme involves optimizing the teaching and learning of accounting principles, practices, and ethics to prepare individuals for the dynamic and evolving demands of

the accounting profession (Akamobi, 2020). As accounting plays a critical role in business, finance, and governance, effectively harnessing accounting education is essential for fostering economic growth, ensuring financial transparency, and promoting ethical business practices

However, this process of harnessing accounting education in universities in Nigeria generally and Enugu State in particular faces several government and institution-related constraints. A constraint is a limitation or restriction that hinders progress, development, or the achievement of goals. Constraints in teaching according to Okeke (2017) are limiting factors or restrictions that hinder the achievement of the goal or full potential of education system. The identification of constraints is primary in navigating through problem-solution.

Government-related constraints are those hindrances that emanate from the government in discharging its responsibility to ensure quality teaching and learning in universities, which, according to (UNESCO, 2020), include funding, provision of facilities, retraining of teachers and effective supervision of curriculum implementation. Government is expected to adequately provide funds, infrastructure, quality personnel, and security for effective harnessing of business education programme but this does not happen as expected in Nigeria. Furthermore, the institution related constraints affect the harnessing of the full potential of accounting education programme in the universities. The institution traditional accounting education curriculum often emphasizes pedagogy, financial accounting and auditing, with limited focus on emerging areas such as sustainability, forensic accounting, and digital finance. This creates a gap between academic training and the evolving needs of the society. The institutional related constraints may relate quality of employed lecturers, provision of teaching facilities and supervision of the lecturers in their curriculum implementation strategies. According to Ogbodo (2016), institution administrative strategy is a critical

factor in achieving effective teaching and harnessing the curriculum contents by the students. The lecturers irrespective of gender cannot deliver quality instruction if the institutional constraints are not identified and addressed.

It is imperative to note that harnessing the full potential of accounting education is dependent on the accounting educator's ability to utilize the provided facilities to implement the curriculum in a conducive environment. The benefit of effective harnessing of accounting education includes enhanced professional competences, increased economic development, improved financial transparency and adaptation to industrial changes (Akamobi, 2020). The benefits cannot be achieved if the constraints are not identified and addressed. Hence, the need to determine the constraints to effective harnessing of accounting education programme in universities in Enugu State.

The subjects used in this study are of the opposite genders, male and female. It has to be noted that the question of gender as a factor in the implementation of accounting education curriculum for effective understanding and skill development among students is a complex and controversial one (Ezeugwu and Obayi, 2023). Gender refers to the fact of being a male or a female. There may be varying opinions of male and female accounting education lecturers and students on the constraints for effective harnessing of the full potential of accounting education programme. Understanding the influence of gender is very important as it enhances the promotion of equality, creating inclusive and diverse society, hence, the influence of gender on the respondents mean ratings on the constraints to effective harnessing of the full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

Education is provided to train the human minds and equip individuals with the competences to become relevant to the society. One of the threatening challenges faced by individuals, families and the

nation generally is the massive unemployment of graduates from educational institutions and accounting education graduates are not left out. It is worrisome to note that the potentials of educational programmes like accounting education have not been fully harnessed by the students. This is as a result of constraints that hinder the effective implementation of the programme. The way out for the educational system is to identify the constraints and explore appropriate strategies that will enable the harnessing of the programme potentials for sustainable training of the students.

The researchers observed that many tertiary institution graduates including accounting education graduates roam about the streets aimlessly idling their time, with the option planning and involving criminal activities. These students ought to have been equipped properly with knowledge, skills and attitude to effectively harness their full potential in accounting education programme. The researchers are worried about the increasing rate of accounting education graduate's turnout of universities yearly without the needed knowledge, skills and attitude for self-employment especially in the contemporary society where paid employment is very scarce. This shows that the full potential of the programme is not being effectively harnessed due to certain unacceptable conditions within and outside the universities. Therefore, the problem of this study is that the constraining factors to effective harnessing of the full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State are not clearly known. This made this study imperative in order to provide empirical data for objective remedial actions by relevant stakeholders to ensure employability of graduates of the programme for poverty reduction and national development.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities in

Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Government-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State.
2. Institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State?
2. What are the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significant:

Ho₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Accounting Educators on the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State.

Ho₂ A significant difference does not exist between the mean responses of male and female Accounting Educators on the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of full potential of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State.

Methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Nworgu (2015) defined survey research design as one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few of them within the entire group. Area of the study was Enugu State which is one of the five states in the South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study was 119 (22 counting education lecturers and

97 final year students from the three universities offering Accounting Education in Enugu State. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was not too large.

Data for the study were collected using a four-point rating scale questionnaire containing 20 items in two sections according to the research questions with response options ranging from strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD). The validation of the instrument was done using three experts, two from Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one in Measurement and Evaluation from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education in Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu State. The instrument was trial tested using 20 accounting education lecturers and students in Anambra State who were not in the area of the study. The reliability coefficient yielded 0.79 and 0.74 for the two clusters of the instrument with an overall coefficient value of 0.77 using Cronbach Alpha which showed that the instrument is highly reliable for the study as recommended by Uzoagulu (2013) that reliability index of 0.60 to 1 shows that the instrument could be used for the data collection.

The administration of the questionnaire was carried out using eight research assistants and out of 119 copies of questionnaire distributed 102 copies were properly filled and returned giving 85.71% return rate. Weighted means was used to answer the research questions and standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the opinions of the respondents. Decision on the research questions was made using the lower and upper limits of the mean based on a four-point scale. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The null hypothesis was not significant when the significant value was less than the .05 level of significant and at appropriate degree of freedom; otherwise the null hypothesis was significant. The Statistical Packages Social Science (SPSS) version 25 was used for all the analysis.

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation on the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State N=102

S/N	government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials;	Male N= 39		Female N= 63		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	Inadequate in-service training to accounting educators	3.63	0.54	3.09	0.76	3.33	0.72	Agree
2	Poor financial support from the government.	3.22	0.79	3.06	0.79	3.13	0.79	Agree
3	Government policies do not effectively address the needs for accounting educators	3.12	0.51	3.07	0.47	3.09	0.49	Agree
4	Poor incentives to accounting	3.41	0.63	3.50	0.57	3.46	0.60	Agree
5	Poor teachers' professional development	3.51	0.51	3.50	0.50	3.51	0.50	Strongly Agree
6	Inadequacy/poor attention to facilities maintenance	3.29	0.60	3.33	0.70	3.32	0.66	Agree
7	Poor provision of facilities	3.12	0.60	3.19	0.62	3.16	0.61	Agree
8	Inability of government to provide internet connectivity	3.34	0.53	3.26	0.59	3.29	0.56	Agree
9	Poor supply equipment for online teaching	3.44	0.50	3.22	0.42	3.32	0.47	Agree
10	Inadequate funding for research and development in accounting education	3.24	0.54	3.02	0.53	3.12	0.54	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.33	0.58	3.22	0.60	3.27	0.59	Agree

X= Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

Table 1 indicates that the overall mean scores for item 5 is 3.51 indicating that that the respondents strongly agreed that it is one of the items as government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme in universities in Enugu State. The remaining nine items mean scores ranges from 3.09 to 3.46 depicting that the respondents agree to the items as the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme

potentials in universities in Enugu State. The overall cluster mean score of 3.27 indicates that the respondents agreed that all agree. This implies that the items are the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State. The overall standard deviation for all the items was 0.59 shows that the respondents were homogeneous in their mean ratings.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of male and female respondents on the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	39	.546	100	0.532	.52120	1.05197	NS
Female	63						

Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 100 degree of freedom for the items is 0.546 with a significant value of 0.532 which is greater than the significant level of 0.05. This means that there is no significant difference in the

respondents' mean ratings on the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities in Enugu State, therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation on the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities in Enugu State. N= 102

S/N	institutions related challenges to online teaching of Business Education courses potential in Public universities;	Male N=39		Female N=63		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
11	Insufficient technological infrastructure accounting teaching.	3.10	0.62	3.17	0.57	3.14	0.59	Agree
12	absence of re-training and support for accounting lecturers	3.51	0.51	3.50	0.50	3.51	0.50	Strongly Agree
13	Inadequate technical support staff in teaching accounting	3.10	0.77	3.15	0.81	3.13	0.79	Agree
14	Poor maintenance of facilitate for teaching accounting	3.27	0.45	3.24	0.43	3.25	0.44	Agree
15	Inadequate monitoring/evaluation of curriculum implementation	3.39	0.49	3.37	0.48	3.38	0.49	Agree
16	Non provision of learning resources to accounting lecturers	2.85	0.65	2.83	0.72	2.84	0.69	Agree
17	Inadequate allocation of fund to accounting education programme	3.12	0.81	3.15	0.76	3.14	0.78	Agree
18	Poor methods for assessing student learning outcomes in accounting education	3.29	0.46	3.20	0.41	3.24	0.43	Agree
19	Poor student support services such as tutoring, counseling, and academic advising	3.27	0.67	3.24	0.67	3.25	0.67	Agree
20	Poor collaboration with non-governmental bodies.	3.80	0.40	2.78	0.60	3.22	0.73	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.27	0.58	3.17	0.60	3.21	0.61	Agree

X= Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The analysis of data presented in Table 3 above shows that item 12 has mean score of 3.51 indicating strongly agree. While remaining nine items overall mean score ranges from 2.84 to 3.38 depicting that the respondents agree to the items as the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities in Enugu State. This means that

Business Educators in universities in South East agree to the items as the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities. The overall cluster mean of 3.21 also depicts agree. The standard deviation of 0.61 shows that the respondents have homogeneity in their responses to the items.

Table 4: Summary of t t-test analysis of male and female respondents on the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potential in universities in Enugu State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	39	.710	100	.807	.36244	.82105	NS
Female	63						

The result of data analysis obtained from the t-test in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 100 degree of freedom for the items is 0.710 with a significant value of 0.807. This

means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean responses of male and female Accounting Education lecturers and students on institutions-related constraints to

effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State.

Discussion

The findings of the study indicate that the respondents agreed that there are several government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State. These constraints include; inadequate in-service training of accounting educators, poor financial support from the government, government policies do not effectively address the needs for accounting educators, poor incentives to accounting and poor teachers professional development among others. This finding agrees with LeBlanc (2019) that governments need to implement financial policies that support the expansion of teaching, including subsidies for technology access and grants for course development. Furthermore, the findings show that there was no significant difference in the respondents' mean ratings as a result of gender. This means that both male and female respondents identified with the listed items as the government-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State.

Further, the findings of the study indicate the institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State. The institutions-related constraints include; insufficient technological infrastructure accounting teaching, absence of re-training and support for accounting lecturers, inadequate technical support staff in teaching accounting, poor maintenance of facilities for teaching accounting, inadequate monitoring/evaluation of curriculum implementation, non-provision of learning resources to accounting lecturers, inadequate allocation of fund to accounting education programme, poor methods for assessing student learning outcomes in accounting education, poor student support services

such as tutoring, counseling, and academic advising and poor collaboration with non-governmental bodies. The findings were in consonance with Ogbodo (2016) states that institutions administrators need to address the constraints faced by teachers in infrastructure and technical support staff for quality instructional delivery. Furthermore, the study showed that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female Accounting Education lecturers and students on identified institutions-related constraints. This means that the respondents gender had no influence on the itemized institutions-related constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State.

Conclusion

The study focused on the constraints to effective harnessing of accounting education Programme potentials in universities in Enugu State. The study identified the government related constraints and institution related constraints to effective harnessing of accounting education Programme in universities in Enugu State. The identified constraints depict that any effort towards ensuring that the students harness accounting education programme potentials should consider the findings of the study. These constraints identified have implication to improving the effective teaching of accounting education in universities for the students to harness the curriculum contents.

Based on the findings, the Government and institution administrators in the universities in Enugu State are expected to adopt and practice strategies that will address the identified constraints to effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials. This is pertinent as there is need to achieve the desired growth and sustainable development in the teaching and learning of accounting education in universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Institution administrators should implement policies that will ensure effective harnessing of Accounting Education Programme potentials in Universities.

2. The Business Educators through the findings should develop adequate strategies to address the

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